

CAUSES OF EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT OVERCROWDING
IN A SUBURBAN COMMUNITY HOSPITAL

A Doctoral Project

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By

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ABSTRACT

Emergency department (ED) overcrowding is a serious problem facing the medical community. Overcrowding can lead to increased ED boarding times, which in turn, can lead to not only patient dissatisfaction with their level of care but increased inpatient length of stays and mortality.

Methods

A review of the literature showed many possible contributing factors to this problem, including lack of access to primary care services, holding of certain types of patients for transfer, boarding of admitted patients, and the time of day and day of the week of presentation to the ED. A quantitative, chart review based, quality improvement study was undertaken to identify the possible causes of overcrowding in this suburban community ED.

Results

Our study showed that while ED boarding time and inpatient discharge order to departure time were not statistically significant predictors of the measures of overcrowding, it was found that ED door to medical screening examination (MSE) time was a statistically significant predictor of average ED DC LOS ($r = .939$, $p < .001$), total diversion time ($r < .680$, $p = .001$) and number of diversion instances ($r = .650$, $p = .001$), and admission time of day (TOD) was a statistically significant predictor of average ED

DC LOS ($r = .899$, $p < .001$), total diversion time ($r = .565$, $p = .004$) and number of diversion instances ($r = .541$, $p = .006$).

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INTRODUCTION

Emergency Department (ED) overcrowding, defined as “. . . when the identified need for emergency services exceeds available resources for patient care in the ED . . .” (American College of Emergency Physicians [ACEP], 2013), has become a serious problem resulting in increased patient mortality, increased inpatient length of stay (LOS), and increased hospital costs (Sun et al., 2013). Studies have shown that there is an association between high ED census and an increase in the likelihood of inpatient deaths with increases in hospital LOS (Sun et al., 2013).

One significant factor contributing to ED overcrowding is patient boarding. The American College of Emergency Physicians (2011) has defined boarding as “. . . the practice of holding patients in the ED after they have been admitted to the hospital . . .”. Boarding admitted patients in the ED has been associated with an increase in inpatient mortality with admitted patients being held for an extended time in the ED (Singer, Thode, Viccellio, & Pines, 2011; Chalfin et al., 2007). In 2009, the United States Governmental Accountability Office published a report acknowledging “. . . that one key factor contributing to crowding was the availability of inpatient beds for patients admitted to the hospital from the emergency department . . .” (p. 14). This report made no specific recommendations on the possible solutions for this problem. A national survey showed the median boarding time of admitted patients in the ED is 79 minutes, and found that increased boarding times of greater than two hours had a greater adverse effect on those EDs with larger daily volumes (Pitts, Vaughns, Gautreau, Cogdell, & Meisel, 2014). Furthermore, a study by Krall, Guardiola, and Richmond (2016) showed that increased boarding times in the ED increased overall ED throughput times, where

throughput is the time, in minutes, from patient arrival in the ED until the patient physically leaves the ED. This was corroborated by an international study that showed a statistically significant decrease in compliance with the hospital's policy regarding the throughput goal of ED patients of less than six hours, when one or more boarders were present in the ED (Fogarty, Saunders, & Cummins, 2014).

In addition to the issues with patient mortality and morbidity, hospitals are increasingly preoccupied with finances to help provide the best care. In 2012, The Hospital Value-Based Purchasing program was instituted by the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS, 2017) to tie patient satisfaction to hospital reimbursement. This program places a high priority on patient satisfaction and the patient experience. Therefore, hospitals also must focus on patient satisfaction and the patient experience. Prolonged ED boarding affects patient satisfaction, as boarded patients prefer being on an inpatient floor rather than in the ED while awaiting an inpatient bed (Walsh, Cortez, & Bakhta, 2008).

There have been a variety of strategies to address ED overcrowding. One method of assessing and controlling overcrowding in the ED is the use of the Community Emergency Department Overcrowding Scale (CEDOCS). The CEDOCS is a validated tool that allows a scaling of the severity of ED crowding by calculating an overall score based on variables such as, the number of beds in the ED, the number of patients in the ED, the number of critical care patients, the longest boarder time, and the longest waiting time of a patient in the waiting room (Weiss, Rogers, Maas, Ernst, & Nick, 2014). This score can then be utilized to trigger a response within the hospital to address the overcrowding in the ED. Another tool for assessing ED crowding is the Emergency

Department Work Index (EDWIN), which has also been shown to have a high positive predictive value for ED overcrowding (Jones, Allen, Flottemesch, & Welch, 2006).

However, though these tools acknowledge the problem of overcrowding, it is still up to the facility to put policies into place that outline the steps to be taken in order to move or discharge (DC) the patient in a timely manner.

Some EDs have taken to adding more patient beds. However, studies have shown that the addition of these beds does not necessarily relieve the problem (Khare, Powell, Reinhardt, & Lucenti, 2009). In fact, increasing the number of beds in one study showed that it actually increased the patient's length of stay as the ED's census rose (Mumma, McCue, Li, & Holmes, 2014). Another variable discussed is the timing of inpatient DC in relation to ED boarding (Powell et al., 2012). Other variables such as time of day or day of the week have been discussed as potential causes of ED overcrowding (Perimal-Lewis, Ben-Tovim, Hakendorf, & Thompson, 2014; Perimal-Lewis, Hakendorf, & Thompson, 2015). Therefore, it is important to identify those underlying causes for ED overcrowding and extended boarding times at one's own ED, as they may vary from hospital to hospital, in order to create a workable intervention.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

A review of literature, focused on references related to decreasing patient boarding times in the ED, was performed utilizing the computer databases PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. The search was performed in three sections, including potential causes of ED overcrowding, assessment of ED overcrowding, and effects of ED overcrowding. Only English language articles were included. The search was limited to peer-reviewed journals, wherever possible. Pertinent references cited in other studies were reviewed as well.

Specific search terms for the potential causes of ED overcrowding section of the review included “emergency department overcrowding,” “length of stay,” “customer satisfaction,” “primary care,” and combinations of these terms. Search terms for the assessment of ED overcrowding section included the terms “CEDOCS,” “NEDOCS,” “EDWIN,” “overcrowding,” “transfer of discharged patients,” and combinations of these terms. The final section of the review, effects of ED overcrowding, was searched with the terms “emergency department overcrowding,” “morbidity & mortality,” “ambulance diversion,” “customer satisfaction,” “patient satisfaction,” and combinations of those terms.

Potential Causes of ED Overcrowding

There are many factors that have been recognized to contribute to ED overcrowding. These include lack of access to primary care services (leading to increased non-urgent/non-emergent ED visits), prolonged holding of certain types of patients for transfer, boarding of admitted patients, and the time of day and day of the week of presentation to the ED.

Barriers to Access

Several studies have pointed to the inability of patients to get timely care from their primary care providers (PCP), leading to an increase in non-urgent ED usage, as a factor in ED overcrowding (Brousseau, Bergholte, & Gorelick, 2004; DeLia, 2006; Grumbach, Keane, & Birdman, 1993; Baker, Stevens, & Brook, 1994; Pane, Farner, & Salness, 1991). A study by Brousseau et al. (2006) showed that patients and caregivers that had difficulty accessing primary care services, or had a difficult previous experience with their PCP, were significantly more likely to utilize the ED for non-urgent reasons. In a study by Baker et al. (1994), 16% of the patients surveyed said they utilized the ED as their primary source of ambulatory care services. This group was 25% less likely to utilize primary care services than the other patients. Interestingly, in this same study, although 56% of the surveyed patients stated they had access to primary care services, between 24% and 36% still utilized the ED for their primary care needs (Baker et al., 1994).

Further studies have shown that patients that were uninsured or underinsured and had low income were more likely to cite lack of access to care as the reason for utilizing the ED. Grumbach et al. (1993) found that uninsured patients cited barriers to access of care as the reason for visiting the ED 45% more often than insured patients, and suggested that patients could be referred to outpatient clinics if there was increased access to primary care services for low income populations. Similarly, a study by Pane et al. (1991) showed that self-pay patients or patients on public aid were more likely to have non-urgent ED visits, and that there was an association between patients with annual incomes less than \$10,000 and increased non-urgent ED usage.

It is important to note that the majority of the studies reviewed have taken place in large, urban hospitals that are often academic centers as well. There appears to be room to assess whether the causes that affect the larger, urban facilities also affect the smaller, suburban community facilities in the same manner, or whether there are other variables that lead to overcrowding in these smaller facilities.

Boarding of Psychiatric Patients and Patients Awaiting Transfer

One lesser, although still significant, cause of ED overcrowding cited was the inability to transfer, admit, or discharge psychiatric patients from the ED. In an American College of Emergency Physicians (ACEP, 2008) survey of emergency physicians, 79% of respondents stated they boarded psychiatric patients in the ED, and greater than 60% of psychiatric patients are boarded for more than four hours after the decision to admit the patient had been made, with 6% being boarded in the ED over 24 hours. Factors cited for the prolonged boarding included insurance status, lack of available inpatient beds (especially pediatric and adolescent beds) and waiting for blood alcohol levels to drop to within acceptable limits. Many of these factors, such as insurance status, also speak to barriers to care access. Although the study is limited in that the sample size was relatively small—respondents were 328 members of the ACEP—it is suspected the results are generalizable to the larger population of ED physicians. In our facility in particular, we board psychiatric patients frequently and for long periods of time, due to most of the reasons listed above. Holding of other patients, primarily those awaiting transfer to another hospital or back to their facility of origin, is another possible factor contributing to ED overcrowding, however, little exists in the literature regarding this subject.

Boarding of Admitted Patients

ED boarding of admitted patients has been identified as a key cause of ED overcrowding (Schafermeyer & Asplin, 2003; US Government Accountability Office, 2009). While the US Government study offered no specific suggestions for resolution, Schafermeyer and Asplin (2003) suggested that increased operational efficiency and support, as well as incentives for additional training could resolve the problem. A Centers for Disease Control (CDC, 2012) study showed a positive correlation between the boarding of admitted patients in the ED and prolonged wait times, where the mean wait time in EDs with no boarded patients was 44.1 minutes, compared with 61.3 minutes in EDs with boarded patients. Krall et al. (2016) also found that the presence of ED boarders leads to increases in ED throughput times, with discharged patient LOS increasing from 152.8 minutes when patients were boarded for less than six hours, to 193.7 minutes when patients were boarded for more than six hours. Another study showed that, for each boarded patient in the ED, the ED showed a 0.37% decrease in compliance with its target ED LOS of less than six hours (Fogarty et al., 2104). A national survey by Pitts et al. (2014), divided boarding times into quartiles measured in minutes, with increasing boarding time ranges in each successive quartile. The study suggested that the boarding of admitted patients in the ED affected hospitals with larger volumes more significantly, with a large jump in annual ED visits from the second quartile of boarding times (25-45 minutes), at 18.2 million visits per year for all hospitals in the quartile, to the third (46-86 minutes) and fourth quartiles (87-410 minutes), at 41.3 million and 53.6 million visits per year, respectively. Hospitals falling into the third quartile averaged 30,900 visits per year (Pitts et al., 2014). This volume is similar to our

ED, which sees approximately 29,000 patients per year. As such it would be expected that the mean boarding times in our facility would be similar to the hospitals sampled in the Pitts et al. (2014) study.

Time of Day

Another possible cause of ED overcrowding that has been offered is the effect that time of day may have on ED flow. One Australian study by Perimal-Lewis et al. (2014), showed an increase of triage to admit time of 29% when presenting outside working hours. Similarly, a second study performed by Perimal-Lewis et al. (2015), showed that the time of day a patient presented to the ED had an adverse effect on wait time (WT), and assessment and treatment time (ATT), with WT increasing by 20.29 minutes, and ATT increased by 34.5 minutes when the patient presented outside of working hours, defined as between 8AM and 6PM.

Assessment of ED Overcrowding

Although the definition of overcrowding differs amongst institutions, several tools have been developed to measure ED crowding, including the EDWIN (Bernstein, Verghese, Leung, Lunney, & Perez, 2003), and the National Emergency Department Overcrowding Scale (NEDOCS: Weiss et al., 2004). The EDWIN and NEDOCS were compared to the Real-time Emergency Analysis of Demand Indicators (READI), and the Emergency Department Crowding Scale (EDCS), and showed the highest positive predictive value for ED overcrowding (Jones et al., 2006). The NEDOCS, although showing excellent predictive value for ED overcrowding (Jones et al., 2006), has “. . . only been validated in large academic major trauma centers” (Weiss et al., 2014). The CEDOCS was adapted from the NEDOCS for use in smaller, community EDs, and

measures slightly different variables that are more applicable to the factors faced in smaller, community EDs (Weiss et al., 2014). Our hospital does not currently use a tool to predict overcrowding, rather, it relies on the number of boarded patients in relation to physical beds to claim overcrowded status.

Effects of ED Overcrowding

Literature reviews by Olshaker and Rathlev (2006), and Schafermeyer and Asplin (2003) demonstrate the potential problems caused by ED overcrowding, including the risk of poor outcomes, ambulance diversion, and ambulances being taken out of service. Studies by Walsh et al. (2008), Pines et al. (2008), and Pitts et al. (2014) also show the effects of ED boarding on patient satisfaction and reimbursement.

Morbidity and Mortality

A study by Liu, Thomas, Gordon, Hamedani, & Weissman (2009) showed that, of the 151 patients sampled, 27.8% suffered at least one adverse event as a result of being boarded in the ED, and that these events were more frequent, 35.9%, in boarded patients over the age of 50. Multiple studies have further shown that boarding patients leads to poorer outcomes after the patients leave the ED. Several studies have shown increases in inpatient mortality, and LOS, in association with prolonged ED boarding (Chalfin et al., 2007; Singer et al., 2011; Sun et al., 2013). Chalfin et al. (2007) showed that critically ill patients with a delay greater than six hours in transferring to the intensive care unit (ICU) suffered higher ICU and hospital mortality than those whose transfers were not delayed, 10.7% vs 8.4%. This delay in transfer was associated with an increased inpatient LOS, 7 days vs 6 days. Singer et al. (2011) also found that hospital LOS increased from 5.6 days for patients that boarded for less than two hours in the ED, to 8.7 days for those that

boarded for more than 24 hours. Similarly, a study by Sun et al. (2013) showed 5% greater odds of inpatient mortality on days of ED crowding. All but one of the studies had very large sample sizes, with the studies by Chalfin et al. (2007), Singer et al. (2011), and Sun et al. (2013) having sample sizes of 50,322, 41,256, and 995,379, respectively. The Liu et al. (2009) study had a limited sample size of only 151 patients, and suggested further study of a larger sample size would be beneficial.

Guttman, Schull, Vermeulen, and Stukel (2011) described how the adverse effects of ED overcrowding can spread even to patients who are not admitted to the hospital, showing that, amongst low-acuity patients that are discharged from the ED during shifts with a mean LOS more than six hours the odds ratio for the risk of short term death or admission to the hospital is 1.71, as opposed to 1.66 in those patients who are seen during shifts with a mean LOS less than 1 hour. ED overcrowding also leads to delays in offloading patients from ambulances (Olshaker & Rathlev, 2006; Schefermeyer & Asplin, 2003). Crilly et al. (2015) showed delays in offloading patients from ambulance gurneys of greater than 30 minutes led to increased ED LOS and increased inpatient LOS. Again, these studies were all performed at large, urban, teaching hospitals, so it is uncertain whether the findings are transferrable to smaller hospitals.

Ambulance Diversion

Ambulance diversion is another key indicator of ED overcrowding, and a serious side effect. A literature review by Olshaker and Rathlev (2013), showed that ED overcrowding led to ambulance diversion, and delay of ambulance offload in the ED. This delay of ambulance patient offload has been shown to be related to increased ED and inpatient LOS (Crilly et al., 2015). A large (N=37,999) study performed at a trauma

center and academic teaching hospital in Toronto, Canada, showed that there is a significant increase of ambulance diversion time when there are admitted patients boarded in the ED (6.2 minutes per patient boarded), and when patients are boarded for prolonged periods (11.9 minutes per hour of patient boarding), with nurse staffing and physician on duty having no effect on diversion times (Schull, Lazier, Vermeulen, Mawhinney, & Morrison, 2003).

Patient Satisfaction and Reimbursement

Although often not getting enough attention in the literature, media, and public forums, patient satisfaction and hospital reimbursement are two very important outcome measures to be considered in any conversation about ED overcrowding.

A cross-sectional survey conducted by Walsh et al. (2008), showed that, in a sample of 1222 patients, 65.5% preferred to be boarded in the hallway of an inpatient ward, rather the ED hallway, citing “. . . privacy concerns and noise levels...” (2008). Pines et al. (2008), showed that ED hallway use for boarded patients resulted in lower ED satisfaction, as did prolonged boarding in the ED. Prolonged ED boarding of admitted patients is viewed as an indicator of poor hospital performance (Pitts et al., 2014). Poor ED experience, as quantified by prolonged ED boarding time, is negatively associated with ED satisfaction and is a predictor of satisfaction with the entire hospital stay (Pines et al., 2008). For these reasons, Medicare chose ED boarding as a quality measure in the Hospital Value-Based Payment program (Pitts et al., 2014), which directly affects hospital reimbursement. In 2014, the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) added the metrics of “. . . median time from ED arrival to ED departure for admitted patients . . . ” and, “. . . admit decision time to ED departure time for admitted

patients . . . ” in their list of clinical quality measures.

Proposed Solutions for ED Overcrowding

Several solutions have been proposed for alleviating ED overcrowding. One of the most common suggestions is to increase the number of beds in the ED. Several studies have examined this virtually (computer modelling), and by physically adding beds. Khare et al. (2009) performed a computer model study that showed in an ED with 23 beds and patients departing at a rate of 1 every 10 minutes, ED LOS was 240 minutes, and with 28 beds the ED LOS would be 247 minutes. Similarly, two other studies that examined EDs pre and post physical expansion also showed greater ED LOS times after adding beds. Han et al. (2007) examined an ED before and after expansion from 28 to 53 beds and, noted that pre and post expansion ED LOS were 4.6 hours and 5.6 hours, respectively, and admit hold times increased from 3.0 hours to 4.1 hours. In another study, Mumma et al. (2014) showed increased ED LOS from 160 minutes to 180 minutes after expanding the ED from 33 to 53 beds (see Table 1).

One solution that appears to be effective is expediting discharge of inpatients, thus freeing up beds for admitted patients from the ED. A computer modeling study performed by Powell et al. (2012) suggested that moving inpatient discharge times four hours earlier in the day resulted in complete elimination of ED boarding.

STATEMENT OF PURPOSE

The purpose of this DNP project was to identify the causes of overcrowding in our 14-bed, suburban community hospital ED. A retrospective chart review was conducted for the past year (Jan 2016-Dec 2016) that measured those possible variables that increase ED LOS as an indicator of ED overcrowding. The most common variables, as identified by literature review, were measured through the use of data from the electronic medical record. These data will hopefully shed some light on some new information that may be contributing to the problem of overcrowding in our ED.

LOCAL CONTEXT

The facility of study is a suburban community hospital, with a total of 210 licensed inpatient beds. The ED consists of 14 beds, and is a ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) receiving center, as well as a certified stroke center. In this facility, the median boarding time for admitted patients in the ED for calendar year (CY) 2016 was 127.5 minutes, 48.5 minutes greater than the national median boarding time reported by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC, 2012). This increased patient boarding time leads to a domino effect, wherein the congestion spreads outward from the ED. Patients in the waiting room are waiting longer to be seen and ambulance transports are being diverted (sent to other facilities). Our ED experienced 781.58 diversion hours, the hours the ED was closed to ambulance transports, in 2016. Ambulances that bring the patients directly into the ED are asked to wait in the hallways due to lack of beds. Even though these patients are in the ED, the fact they are delayed placement in a physical ED bed leads to increased ED length of stay (LOS), and hospital LOS (Crilly et al., 2015). This does not just compromise patient safety, as the ED is unable to accommodate new patients when physical beds are not available, but also translates to a financial loss for the hospital. By dividing 781.58 diversion hours by 24 hours, it computes to 33 days of diversion. With an average of 81 patients per day, at an average cost-per-case of \$570.00 in 2016, diversion of ambulances from our ED cost approximately \$1.5 million in lost revenue for the department in 2016 (R. Madhukumar, personal communication, September 13, 2016).

A previous throughput quality improvement (QI) project conducted by our ED in 2015 evaluated the function of the ED and how it related to patient boarding. Several

factors were evaluated and modified. These included the initial medical screening examination (MSE) of the patient, often referred to as the “door-to-doc” time, which is the time from initial patient presentation to the ED to the first encounter with the medical provider, and the “door-to-decision” time, the time from initial ED arrival to the attending medical provider’s decision to discharge, admit, or transfer a patient. Time goals were set and by the end of the project, were met by the ED. The issue of prolonged MSE times was addressed by distributing phones to the ED charge nurse and the ED triage nurse. When a patient checked in, the triage phone was called, and the triage nurse came to the triage room and triaged the patient. This decreased the time the patient waited between check-in and triage. When triage was completed, the triage nurse assigned a triage value of 1-5 based on the Emergency Severity Index (ESI), where 1 was the least serious, and 5 was critical. If the patient was a level 1-3, an attempt was made to immediately place the patient in an ED bed, if one was available. If an ED bed was not available, the triage nurse would notify a provider—a nurse practitioner (NP), physician assistant (PA), or medical doctor (MD)—who would go to triage and perform a basic interview and examination, and then order appropriate testing to begin the treatment process. If the patient was a level 4 or 5, and the Fast Track (FT) was open, the patient would be sent there. Otherwise, once the provider assessed the patient, and any pertinent orders were placed in order to begin the treatment process (see Figure 1), the patient would then be sent back out to the waiting room (WR).

The ED was able to shorten LOS by beginning the treatment and diagnosis of the patient earlier in the process by implementing this MSE as described above, and by getting ancillary departments such as laboratory and radiology to perform the ordered

procedures and tests in a timelier manner. During this project, however, the actual time of ED boarding, once the patient is assigned an inpatient bed, and inpatient discharge times were not measured. Therefore, even with the implementation of these new interventions, the overcrowding in our ED remains a problem. In order to solve the problem of overcrowding, it is important to further identify the underlying causes of ED overcrowding at each facility in order to develop a plan to correct the problem.

FRAMEWORK

The framework that was used for this DNP project is based on LEAN principles. LEAN is not an acronym, rather, it reflects the idea of streamlined processes. LEAN principles focus on how to “. . . maximize customer value while minimizing waste . . .” (Lean Enterprise Institute, 2017). The LEAN principles were originally intended for manufacturing processes, and were developed by Womack in the late 1980s. LEAN has since been used successfully in other areas, including healthcare and government (Lean Enterprise Institute, n.d.). LEAN principles have been successfully applied several times in the hospital setting to decrease ED overcrowding. A study by Dickson, Singh, Cheung, Wyatt, and Nugent (2009) showed that, following a LEAN process study, ED LOS times decreased and patient satisfaction improved in the year following the study, despite a 9.23% increase in the number of patient visits. Another study demonstrated a decrease in registration to physician assessment times of 30%, and a decrease in LOS from a mean of 3.6 hours to 2.8 hours (Ng, Vail, Thomas, & Schmidt, 2010). A LEAN project in our own 7-hospital corporation showed application of LEAN principles to ED problems improved LOS times in the ED from 193 minutes to 182 minutes, decreased the number of patients who left without being seen from 1.6% to 0.6%, and decreased door to provider times from an average of 37 minutes to an average of 31 minutes, across the system (Chiu, Tsai, & Hwong, 2016).

LEAN focuses on three main issues: purpose, process, and people. The purpose is what goal the organization is hoping to accomplish, which is to decrease ED overcrowding in our hospital.

The term process refers to an assessment to determine where the shortcomings are

before developing a plan to address them. The assessment in our project will be performed by a LEAN team, made up of representatives of the key stakeholders. The LEAN term “people” refers to ensuring that someone is responsible for monitoring the process, and that all the stakeholders are identified, have been “bought in” to the change, and are actively involved. For this project, once the data are analyzed, it will be shared with the stakeholders, which include the floor nurses, charge nurses, environmental services (EVS), admitting, case management, unit directors, and ED providers in hopes that a new policy will be formulated to decrease ED overcrowding in our facility.

Figure 2 depicts the basic LEAN model adapted for this study. Application of the LEAN model to the issue of ED overcrowding in our hospital would begin at the “Start” by identifying the problem, in this case, ED overcrowding as evidenced by increased ED LOS and ambulance diversion times. “Step 1” consists of identifying the potential causes of ED overcrowding, which is the purpose of this project. “Step 2” is choosing an addressable cause, for example, delay in DC from the inpatient floor. In this case, “Step 3” would be to implement an intervention, such as a checklist or huddle, to a single unit. At the “Decision” junction, we would assess whether the intervention improved the ED overcrowding. If so, then we continue on to “Step 4” which, in our example, would be to apply the intervention on a hospital-wide basis, and follow up for sustainability. If the intervention does not improve the problem, we return to “Step 2”. The “End” of the process would be elimination of ED overcrowding.

METHOD

The purpose of this project was to determine the factors contributing to ED overcrowding in a suburban, community hospital. By analyzing available data, and determining possible causes, a plan can then be implemented to alleviate the problem. In the section below, the methods for this quality improvement (QI) project are described. See Appendix for the proposed project timeline.

Setting

This quality improvement (QI) project took place at a 210-bed suburban medical center, with a 14-bed ED. The facility is located in Monterey Park, California, in the heart of the San Gabriel Valley of the County of Los Angeles. This community has a large Asian immigrant population, many of whom have recently arrived in the United States, and have little to no primary care access. The hospital has three Intensive Care Units (ICU), a cardiac catheterization laboratory, a maternity unit, and a neonatal ICU. The hospital does not have an inpatient pediatric unit.

The ED, which has been designated as a ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction (STEMI) receiving center and a primary stroke center, sees approximately 29,000 patients per year. It is separated into the main ED, consisting of 14 beds, and a FT unit, consisting of 3 beds and multiple patient examination chairs. The ED sees a broad mix of patients, with a large population of chronically ill adults with multiple comorbidities. The ED also sees walk-in pediatric patients, but is not an Emergency Department Approved for Pediatrics (EDAP) and, therefore, does not accept pediatric paramedic runs. The hospital has no inpatient pediatric beds, necessitating that all pediatric patients requiring admission must be transferred. The ED also serves as a teaching site for

Physician Assistant (PA) and Doctor of Osteopathic Medicine (DO) students.

The ED is usually staffed with registered nurses (RN) at a state-mandated 4 patients to 1 RN ratio. There is an emergency physician from 0700 until 1900, and again from 1900 to 0700. Additionally, there is an advanced practice provider (APP)—PA or NP—from 1000 until 2200, and another from 1400 until 0200. The 1000 APP usually staffs the main side of the ED, while the 1400 APP staffs the FT until 2200 and then rotates to the main ED until 0200. This hospital utilizes the CPSI electronic health record (EHR) system, which allows for tracking of all pertinent variables and ease of retrieval.

Sample

The project involved a retrospective review of medical chart data. All patient charts for patients over the age of 18 years presenting to the ED for a twelve-month period, starting January 1, 2016 and ending December 31, 2016, and that had ED LOS greater than 120 minutes were included. The ED LOS time of greater than 120 minutes has been chosen for the reason that this is the facility goal for ED throughput. Patients that stay in the ED longer than this are the population of interest, as increased ED LOS is an indicator of crowding. This included those patients who had been admitted from the ED to an inpatient area, as well as those patients that had been directly discharged from our ED or left without being seen. A mixed-use telemetry and medical surgical floor, 3 East, receives a large portion of the ED admits on a daily basis, and was the only inpatient floor addressed in this project. Exclusion criteria included patients under the age of 18, and those patients that expire. These criteria resulted in a sample size of 7018 charts.

Ethical Issues

Before the project began, the Institutional Review Board (IRB) staff at the facility was contacted to determine whether this project required hospital IRB submission. Since all retrospective chart review data obtained for this QI project was de-identified and used as aggregate data, this project was exempt from IRB review. Following this determination, an application was submitted to IRB at the California State University at Los Angeles (CSULA) and was approved.

Planning the Quality Improvement Study

The project and its purpose were discussed with the administration, and other key stakeholders. This included the Chief Executive Officer (CEO), Chief Nursing Officer (CNO), Assistant CNO, Nursing Director of 3 East, the medical and nursing directors of the ED, and IT staff. Informal discussions with the CEO, CNO and Assistant CNO, and IT took place, and they were receptive to the project. A formal meeting with the above stakeholders was set, and details of the project were discussed. All of the above-mentioned staff have a vested interest in the outcomes of the project, and were willing to contribute.

Data collection was done through the hospital's EHR, with the assistance of the IT staff and QI director. Based on a literature review, common variables that often lead to ED overcrowding and prolonged boarding times of admitted patient in EDs, as well as other possible confounding variables, were analyzed. We analyzed trends in 1) mean DC order to departure time from inpatient floor, 2) mean ED door to provider times, 3) mean ED boarding times and, 4) time of day of admission. Mean ED DC LOS, total ambulance diversion minutes, and ambulance diversion instances were measured as

outcome variables.

The chart audit covered a period of 12 months, to give an adequate sample and allow for variability across the seasons. The 12-month period covered the 2016 calendar year, from January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2016.

Operational Definition of Variables

This was a non-experimental, retrospective chart review study. The predictor variables (PV) for this study included mean inpatient DC time, mean ED door to medical screening examination (MSE) time, mean ED boarding time, admission time of day (TOD) and psychiatric patient hold times. Mean inpatient DC order to departure time is the average time, in minutes, between the time the inpatient attending physician enters the order for the patient to be discharged and the time the patient physically leaves the inpatient floor, with a facility-set goal of 90 minutes or less. Mean ED door to MSE time is the average time, in minutes, between the patients' check-in and the time the ED provider, such as a physician, NP, or PA evaluates the patient, with a target goal of 30 minutes or less. Mean ED boarding time is defined as the time, in minutes, between the ED provider's decision to admit the patient and the time the patient physically leaves the department, with the national average being 70 minutes (CDC, 2009).

The outcome variables (OV) measured were mean ED DC LOS, ambulance diversion time, and instances of ambulance diversion. Mean ED DC LOS was measured as the LOS, in minutes, of patients who are eventually discharged from the ED, with a target time of 120 minutes or less. Ambulance diversion times were measured as the time, in minutes, that the ED was closed to paramedic ambulance transports in a given one-hour block over the course of the year. Instances of ambulance diversion are defined

by the number of times the ED went on ambulance diversion in a given one-hour block, over the course of the year. Ambulance diversion times, instances of ambulance diversion, and ED DC LOS were used as proxies for overcrowding.

Through analysis of these data, we hoped to gain insight as to which variables affect ED crowding the most. Once these variables were identified and isolated, the information generated could then be utilized to plan and implement a change project.

Method of Evaluation

The data from this retrospective chart audit were collected and organized by time of day, in one hour blocks, to allow for analysis. Utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS™) electronic software, multiple linear regressions were performed. Each linear regression analyzed the four PVs (inpatient DC time, ED door to MSE time, ED boarding time, and admission TOD), in relation to each individual OV (ED DC LOS, ED diversion time, and ED diversion instances). Then, the Pearson correlation between each individual PV and OV was obtained.

RESULTS

Data from all ED admissions were initially reviewed in their raw form. They were then filtered according to the inclusion/exclusion criteria. We were unable to obtain data on psychiatric patient holds by hour, therefore, this variable was excluded from analysis. We had originally intended to use mean diversion time as an OV. However, examination of the data showed that the mean diversion time was usually 60 minutes. This is due to the fact that diversion automatically cancels after 60 minutes. Therefore, no matter how many times the ED was on diversion during a given hour, the mean would be 60 minutes. The decision was made to substitute the total amount of time the ED was on diversion and the total instances of ED diversion as more accurate and representational outcome metrics.

For analyses, mean scores were calculated for inpatient DC time (overall $M = 400.6$, $SD = 361.8$), ED door to MSE time (overall $M = 28.19$, $SD = 10.64$), ED boarding time (overall $M = 224.22$, $SD = 28.78$), and ED DC LOS (overall $M = 140.15$, $SD = 17.71$) for each hour of the day. Total ED diversion time and total instances of ED diversions were calculated by summing the values of the variables for each hour of the day, across the year of the study. TOD was entered as values ranging from 0 to 23 to indicate the hour of the day, with 0 representing the 12am hour and 23 representing the 11pm hour.

Pearson product-moment correlations were calculated to explore the relationships between the predictor variables and the outcome variables. Average ED door to MSE time and admission TOD were significantly correlated to ED DC LOS, total diversion time and number diversion instances. Average boarding time and ED DC LOS were

significantly correlated, however average boarding time was not significantly correlated to total diversion time and number of diversion instances. Interestingly, inpatient DC time and average ED DC LOS, total diversion time and number of diversion instances showed a significant negative correlation. Therefore, when the inpatient orders to discharge decreased, the values of the outcome variables increased. See Table 2 for r -values and their corresponding significance levels.

Multiple regressions analyses were conducted to determine if mean inpatient DC time, mean ED door to MSE time, mean ED boarding time, and admission TOD predicted our measures of ED overcrowding (mean ED DC LOS, total ED diversion time, and number of instances of ED diversions).

Mean ED DC LOS

A multiple regression analysis revealed that the predictor variables explained 89.9% of the variance in mean ED DC LOS ($F(4, 19) = 42.202, p < .001, R^2 = .899$). However, only ED door to MSE time was a significant predictor of ED DC LOS ($\beta = .683, p = .002$), such that as ED door to MSE increased, ED DC LOS also increased. DC time ($\beta = -.04, p = .739$), ED boarding time ($\beta = .173, p = .307$), and TOD ($\beta = .096, p = .689$), were not significant predictors of ED DC LOS.

Total ED Diversion Time

A second multiple regression analysis indicated that the predictor variables accounted for 61.1% of the variance in total ED diversion time ($F(4, 19) = 7.455, p = .001, R^2 = .611$). Although none of the predictor variables reached statistical significance, both ED door to MSE and DC time were marginally significant predictors. Specifically, as total ED diversion time tended to increase, ED door to MSE increased

($\beta = .68, p = .087$), and DC time decreased ($\beta = -.421, p = .084$). Neither ED boarding time ($\beta = -.366, p = .273$), nor TOD ($\beta = .029, p = .95$) predicted total diversion time.

Number of Diversion Instances

A final multiple regression analysis showed that the predictor variables explained 61.3% of the variance in number of diversion instances ($F(4, 19) = 7.511, p = .001, R^2 = .613$). Again, none of the predictor variables reached statistical significance. However, both ED door to MSE ($\beta = .651, p = .099$), and ED boarding time ($\beta = -.594, p = .082$) were marginally significant predictors of number of diversion instances. That is, the number of diversion instances tended to increase, as ED door to MSE increased, and ED boarding time decreased. Neither DC time ($\beta = -.376, p = .273$), nor TOD ($\beta = .207, p = .658$) predicted number of diversion instances.

Further examination of the quantitative data also showed an *increase* in average ED door to MSE time, average ED boarding time and ED DC LOS between 1000 and 1900, while inpatient DC time was actually *decreasing* (see Figure 3). We noted the three highest values for mean ED door to provider time, mean ED boarding time and mean ED DC LOS between the hours of 1000 and 1900 (see Figure 4). During this time, we also noted the highest number of patients admitted per hour, and highest instances of ED diversion.

DISCUSSION

This study sought to identify the variable or variables that led to overcrowding in a suburban community ED. When the data were initially reviewed, it was noted that nearly 85% of all diversion times/instances were logged as due to excessive ED boarding. Therefore, the natural assumption was that this, along with increased inpatient DC order to departure times, would be the main cause of ED overcrowding. However, when the statistical analyses were run, we found that these actually had *no* statistically significant effect on the measures of overcrowding (ED DC LOS, total diversion times, and instances of diversion).

What we found, instead, was that only mean ED door to provider time and time of day of admission showed a statistically significant increases in our ED overcrowding measures. When we compared the longest ED door to provider times—times that spiked above the institution's 30-minute goal—we found they corresponded with the most patients admitted per hour during those times, the most instances of diversion, and the highest total diversion times. This block of time spanned the hours of 1000-1900 daily.

During this same time period, the mean inpatient DC order to departure times decreased, indicating that inpatient nursing staff were able to discharge patients more efficiently. Although the reason is unclear at this time, it may be due to the subject unit being at its full staffing levels during this period. Also, although mean ED boarding times were highest during this period, they had no statistically significant effect on the outcome measures.

The data also showed that there was a steady decrease in mean ED door to provider times, number of admissions per hour, and the outcome variables between 0000

and 0200 daily.

Limitations

There were several limitations to this study. Firstly, we were unable to obtain data relating to psychiatric patient transfer holds and patients who left without being seen. Other data that may have proved valuable for our analyses included number of patients checking in per hour. This study was also limited to the ED and one inpatient floor. This did not allow for analyses of discharge times from the critical care units and other units that may directly affect our findings.

Implications for Practice

When the data are taken together as a whole, it is clear that the overcrowding problem as indicated by the outcome variables begins at approximately 1000 daily. Increased mean ED door to MSE times, and number of admissions per hour to the inpatient area, correlate with the increases in our outcome variables during this time frame. Currently, ED provider staffing at this time of day is a physician and an APP in the main ED. The FT APP is scheduled to arrive at 1400, leaving four hours between the onset of the overcrowding, as indicated in the data, and the FT APP arrival. Therefore, the significant variables must be addressed. As there is no way to control the flow of patients into the ED other than through diversion – multiple instances of which are one of the issues of concern – efforts should focus on ED door to MSE times.

One proposed solution is to move the arrival of the FT APP to 1200 (noon). This would bring in the additional provider earlier in the process, possibly avoiding the overcrowding issues by lowering ED door to MSE times, before they increase above the 30-minute goal. This would result in the FT APP shift ending at 0000 (midnight).

Although this leaves the night physician with single coverage after this time, the data show that patient admissions per hour, mean ED boarding time, mean ED DC LOS, mean diversion times, and instances of diversion all steadily decrease after this time.

We believe that instituting this change, with stakeholders' buy in, can result in an overall decrease in average ED DC LOS, ambulance diversion instances, and total ambulance diversion times. This can, in turn, lead to decreased patient wait times, increased patient satisfaction, and decreased morbidity and mortality.

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APPENDIX A
TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1

Studies Examining ED Expansion on LOS

Authors, Year	Type of Expansion	Pre-Expansion	Post-Expansion
Han, et al., 2007	Physical	276	336
Khare, et al., 2009	Computer model	240	247
Mumma, et al., 2014	Physical	160	180

Note. Mean ED LOS presented in minutes for pre and post ED expansion.

Table 2

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficients for Predictor and Outcome Variables

PV	OV		
	ED DC LOS	Total ED diversion time	Number of diversion instances
Mean inpatient DC time	-.719**	-.72**	-.699**
Mean ED to MSE time	.939**	.68**	.65**
Mean ED boarding time	.826**	.379 [†]	.313
Admission TOD	.899**	.565**	.541**

Note. Values presented in the table are r -values (** $p \leq .01$, * $p \leq .05$, [†] $p \leq .10$).

Figure 1. ED triage, ordering, and bed placement process. (WR = waiting room, FT = fast track).

Figure 2. Basic LEAN model diagram. Adapted from Parker, 2014. Retrieved from <https://www.leansigmacorporation.com/how-to-define-a-process/>

Figure 3. The relationship between mean inpatient order to DC time, mean ED door to MSE time, mean ED boarding time, and mean length of stay by hour of day.

Figure 4. Mean times in minutes for each variable measured between the hours of 0300-2300.

APPENDIX B

IRB APPROVAL LETTER

Office Memorandum

DATE: July 26, 2017

TO: Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP- BC
 FROM: California State University, Los Angeles
 Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1082639-1] Causes of
 Emergency Department Overcrowding in a
 Suburban Community Hospital

REFERENCE #: 16-248
 SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: APPROVED
 APPROVAL DATE: July 26, 2017
 EXPIRATION DATE: July 25, 2018
 REVIEW TYPE: Expedited Review

REVIEW CATEGORY: Expedited review category # 5

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has APPROVED your submission. This approval is based on an appropriate risk/benefit ratio and a project design wherein the risks have been minimized. All research must be conducted in accordance with this approved submission.

This submission has received Expedited Review based on the applicable federal regulation.

Please make sure that you follow the procedures for informed consent outlined in the APPROVED proposal as required by federal regulations.

Please note that any modification to previously approved materials must be approved by this committee prior to initiation. Please use the appropriate modification forms for this procedure.

All UNANTICIPATED PROBLEMS involving risks to subjects or others and SERIOUS and UNEXPECTED adverse events must be reported promptly to irb@calstatela.edu using the "Adverse Effects Report Form." All federal and sponsor reporting requirements should also be followed.

All NON-COMPLIANCE issues or COMPLAINTS regarding this project must be reported promptly to this office.

This project has been determined to be a project. Based on the risks, this project requires continuing review by this committee on an annual basis. Please use the appropriate forms for this procedure. Your documentation for continuing review must be received with sufficient time for review and continued approval before the expiration date of July 25, 2018.

Please note that all research records must be retained for a minimum of three years after the completion of the project.

If you have any questions, please contact Claire Bakewell at irb3@calstatela.edu or irb@calstatela.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX C

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Causes of Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Lack of Primary Care

Article (Author(s), Year) Purpose Here	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Regular Source of Ambulatory Care and Medical Care Utilization by Patients Presenting to a Public Hospital Emergency Department. (Baker, et al., 1994)	Cross-Sectional Survey IDV: Reg source of care, health status, PCP visits DV: ED usage	Public Hospital N=1190	Self-reported reg source of care, health status, recent PCP visits	ED reg source of care= 16%, Poor health= 25% of above Physician visits= this group 25% fewer Had PCP= 56% 24%-36% regular care visits in ED	Rely heavily on ED for ambulatory care even if they had PCP Pts who identify ED as reg source of care used PCP services < pts w/ access PCP in other settings.
The effect of prior interactions with a primary care provider on nonurgent pediatric emergency department use. (Brousseau, et al., 2004)	Case-control study IDV: Prev interactions w/PCP DV: Non-urgent ED use	Pediatric ED in urban Pediatric hospital N=719	CAHPS= pt satisfaction survey - diff mtg med needs	Diff mtg med needs w/o long waits= increased non-urg ED usage (p<0.001)	Prev diff accessing PCP= increased non-urgent ED use
Potentially avoidable use of hospital emergency departments in New Jersey. (DeLia, 2006)	IDV: Dx, insurance status, age, gender	N= 2.46 million non-admitted ED pts in NJ, 2004		primary care treatable ED visits= 49% between 8a-5p	Non-emergent and primary care visits = large % of ED use

Article (Author(s), Year) Purpose Here	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
	DV: ED usage			Non-emergent between= 50% between 8a-5p	Poss barrier to PCP access or unhappy w/ PCP
Primary care and public emergency department overcrowding. (Grumbach, et al., 1993)	Cross-sectional survey IDV: PCP access, willing to use non-ED svcs DV: ED usage	Large urban teaching hospital N=700		Uninsured cited barriers to access 45% more often than insured (p<0.001)	ED could refer pt to PCP if increased avail for low income pop
Health Care Access Problems of Medically Indigent Emergency Department Walk-in Patients. (Pane, et al., 1991)	Survey IDV: Insurance status, income level, PCP access, refusal of care at other ED, delay in seeking healthcare DV: ED usage	Large, urban Level I teaching hospital N=940 OB pt excluded		Public aid/Self-pay assoc w/ routine use of ED (p<0.003) Income <\$10,000 assoc w/routine ED use (p<0.02)	Income <\$10,00 and those with public aid/self-pay insurance more likely to use the ED for routine care

*Note.*DBN=discharge before noon; DC=discharge(d); DCLOS=EDLOS for DC pt; ED=Emergency Department; EDLOS=ED Length of Stay; LWBS=left without being seen; MICU=Medical Intensive Care Unit; MSE=Medical Screening Exam; PPD=pt per day; pt=patient

Causes of Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Boarding of Patients

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
ACEP psychiatric and substance abuse survey 2008. (ACEP, 2008)	Cross sectional survey online	ED physicians N=328		79% board psych pt 60% psych pt board >4 hrs 33% psych pt board >8 hrs 6% psych pt board over 24 hrs insurance barriers, no beds, ETOH level normalization	Limited study by size Only ACEP members
The Effect of Boarders on Emergency Department Process Flow. (Fogarty, et al. 2014)	Retrospective IDV: Number boarded patients DV: Target ED LOS	University Hospital N=114,836	Number of ED boarders: Not clearly defined Target ED LOS= ED LOS<6h	0.37% Decrease in compliance w/ <6h EDLOS target per boarder in the ED	Presence of ED boarders leads to incr ED LOS
Increased door to admission time is associated with prolonged throughput for ED patients discharged home. (Krall, et al, 2016)	Prospective analysis IDV: ED LOS for admitted patients DV: median DCLOS	Inner city ED N=24,127	ED LOS for admitted patients= LOS of patients being held after inpatient admission,2 groups (<6hrs, >6hrs) Median DCLOS= Average LOS of patients DC to home	Median DC LOS w/ ED LOS ≥6hrs= 193.7min Median DC LOS w/ ED LOS <6hrs= 152.8mins	Prolonged ED stays for admitted pts assoc with prolonged throughput times for pts DC home from the ED.
A Cross-sectional Study of Emergency Department Boarding	Cross-sectional retrospective	National Hospital Ambulatory Medical Care Survey	ED boarding times= Time admitted patients spent in the ED after	National Median Boarding= 79min	In nat'l survey, ED boarding of admitted pts disproportionately

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Practices in the United States. (Pitts, et al, 2014)	IDV: ED boarding times DV: Average ED visits	N=139,502	admission Average ED visits= Average number of annual ED visits per hospital in the quartile (in thousands)	1 st Quartile (0-24min)= 16.0 avg annual visits/hosp 2 nd Quartile (25-45min)= 18.4 avg annual visits/hosp 3 rd Quartile (46-86min)= 30.9 avg annual visits/hosp 4 th Quartile (87-410min)= 39.9 avg annual visits/hosp	affects hospitals w/ higher ED volumes Prolonged ED boarding viewed as poor hosp perf Chosen as quality measure in HVBP (affects reimbursement)
Hospital and Emergency Department Crowding in the United States. (Schafermeyer, et al, 2003)	Literature review	NA	NA	Overcrowding leads to Diversion Main cause is inpatient boarding	Potential solutions: Increased operational efficiency Policy changes: appropriate reimbursement ED boarding is inappropriate Additional support and incentives for training Appropriate tort reform

Note. DBN=discharge before noon; DC=discharge(d); DCLOS=EDLOS for DC pt; ED=Emergency Department; EDLOS=ED Length of Stay; LWBS=left without being seen; MICU=Medical Intensive Care Unit; MSE=Medical Screening Exam; PPD=pt per day; pt=patient

Causes of Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Time of Day/Day of Week

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Characteristics favouring a delayed disposition decision in the Emergency Department (Perimal-Lewis, et al., 2015)	Retrospective cohort study IDV: Pt in ED, time of assessment DV: ATT, WT	Urban tertiary care hospital-Australia N=255,640	Working hours= 0800-1800 Waiting time (WT)=door to ED MD Assessment and treatment time (ATT)=doc to dispo time Admission delay time (ADT)=dispo to departure	+10pt in ED= WT+19.9min (p<0.001) ATT+35.9min (p<0.001) Init assess outside working hours= ATT+34.5min (p<0.001) WT+20.29min (p<0.001) Incr WT effect on ATT negligible	Crowding incr WT/ATT Init assessment outside working hrs incr WT/ATT
Emergency department lengths of stay: characteristics favouring a delay to the admission decision as distinct from a delay while awaiting an inpatient bed (Perimal-Lewis, et al., 2014)	Retrospective cohort study IDV: triage time DV: ED LOS, triage to admit time, boarding time	Urban, tertiary care, teaching ED N=19,476	Working hours =0800-1800 Triage time= time of presentation to ED for triage Triage to admit time (TTA)= time from triage until decision to admit pt ED LOS= time pt in ED from triage to departure	+1 ED pt= TTA+ 0.82% (p<0.001) +1 ED pt=boarding time +10 min (p<0.001) Present outside working hours= TTA+29%	Overcrowding incr TTA, and Boarding times Presenting outside work hours incr TTA

*Note.*DBN=discharge before noon; DC=discharge(d); DCLOS=EDLOS for DC pt; ED=Emergency Department; EDLOS=ED Length of Stay; LWBS=left without being seen; MICU=Medical Intensive Care Unit; MSE=Medical Screening Exam; PPD=pt per day; pt=patient

Measurements of Overcrowding Table of Evidence

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Development and validation of a new index to measure emergency department crowding. (Bernstein, et al, 2003)	Prospective tool development	Urban teaching ED N=2,647	Emergency Department Work Index (EDWIN)= “patient triage units per attending physician per available bed.” Triage Category 1-5, 5 is most acute	EDWIN scores compared w/mean of Nurse/physician Likert scores for busyness/crowdedness, w/excellent correlation (p<0.0001) A strong association was found between EDWIN scores and diversion. (p<0.001)	EDWIN correlated w/staff assessment of ED crowding/diversion. Can be programmed to alert staff when the ED is approaching crisis.
An independent evaluation of four quantitative emergency department crowding scales. (Jones, et al, 2006)	retrospective	N=135	Sensitivity Specificity Positive predictive value (PPV)	NEDOCS: Most reliable Sensitivity (0.81) Specificity (0.87) PPV (0.62) EDWIN: Sensitivity (0.81) Specificity (0.76) PPV (0.47)	EDWIN and NEDOCS, had good predictive power (AROC >0.80) of perceived ED crowding, Can be used effectively after site-specific calibration
Estimating the degree of emergency department overcrowding in academic medical centers: results of the National ED Overcrowding Study (NEDOCS). (Weiss, et al, 2004)	Prospective tool development IDV: ED census DV: Average perception of ED MD or RN of ED overcrowding compared to	Academic medical centers N=336		23 Question form showed high predictive value. Scaled-down 5 question version predicted the full model with 88% accuracy	Results of a five-question reduced model are valid and accurate in predicting the degree of overcrowding in academic centers.

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
	predictive model				
Evaluating community ED crowding: the Community ED Overcrowding Scale study (Weiss, et al, 2014)	Prospective study DV: Average perception of ED MD or RN of ED overcrowding in a community hospital	13 community hospitals in California N=1489		Of 20 possible variables, 5 variables were found to explain 92% of the variability of full model	Five variables Correlated with community ED crowding Can model full NEDOCS

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Effects of Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Morbidity and Mortality/Diversion

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Impact of delayed transfer of critically ill patients from the emergency department to the intensive care unit. (Chalfin et al, 2007)	Cross-sectional IDV: Time to ICU transfer from ED DV: Inpatient LOS, ICU mortality	ED and ICU N=50,322	Delayed ED to ICU transfer= delay of transfer from ED to ICU >6hours Inpatient LOS=days of inpatient stay delayed v non=delayed ICU mortality= percent mortality delayed v non-delayed	Inpatient LOS (delayed/non-delayed)= 7days/6days ICU mortality (delayed/non-delayed)= 10.7%/8.4%	Critically ill ED pts w/>6-hr delay in ICU transfer had incr hospital LOS and higher ICU and hosp mortality.
Improved outcomes for emergency department patients whose ambulance off-stretcher time is not delayed. (Crilly, et al. 2015)	Retrospective IDV: Ambulance offload time (AOT) DV: ED LOS, Inpatient LOS	multi-site N=40,783	ED LOS: Total length of stay in the ED (min) Inpatient LOS: Total length of stay in the hospital (days)	ED LOS (non-delayed/delayed): HospA=333/373 HospB=265/357 HospC=308/386 Inpatient LOS (non-delayed/delayed): HospA=2/3 HospB=2/3 HospC=2/1.5	AOT < 30 min leads to better outcomes
Association between waiting times and short term mortality and hospital admission after departure from emergency department: population based cohort study from Ontario,	Retrospective cohort study IDV: ED LOS DV: Risk of adverse events	Multiple high-volume ED N=14,551,553 Seen and DC N=13,934,542 LWBS	Risk of adverse events= admission to hospital or death within 7 days	Risk of adverse events with ED LOS ≥ 6 h v <1h: odds ratio for death/admission in acutely ill= 1.79/1.95 odds ratio for death/admission in low acuity= 1.71/1.66	Presentation to ED during shifts with longer mean LOS assoc w/ greater risk in the short term of death and admission to hospital in pts well enough to be

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Canada. (Guttman, et al, 2011)		N=617,011			DC/LWBS
A pilot study examining undesirable events among emergency department–boarded patients awaiting inpatient beds. (Liu, et al, 2009)	Chart review IDV: Boarded patient in ED DV: Frequency of undesirable events	Level I trauma, tertiary, urban teaching hospital N=151	Frequency of adverse event= occurrence (%) of missed medication, missed lab evaluations, ED death, aspiration, hypotension, hypoxia, arrhythmia and others	Pt w/ at least 1 adverse event= 27.8%	A sig freq of adverse events occurs while pts board in the ED. Events are more frequent in older pts, pts w/ more comorbidities.
Emergency Department Overcrowding and Ambulance Diversion: The Impact and Potential Solutions of Extended Boarding of Admitted Patients in the Emergency Department. (Olshaker, et al, 2006)	Literature Review	NA	NA	Overcrowding has many potential detrimental effects: diversion of ambulances, frustration for patients and ED personnel, greater risk for poor outcomes. ambulances stranded in EDs unable to transfer patients	Potential solutions: Increasing capacity Increasing efficiency
Emergency department contributors to ambulance diversion: a quantitative analysis. (Schull, et al., 2013)	Retrospective chart review IDV: Admitted pts, nurse hours, physician on duty DV: ambulance diversion times	Urban trauma center, teaching hospital N=37,999	Admitted pt= Admitted pt held in ED Nurse hours= nurses on shift Ambulance diversion times=time in minutes ambulances are diverted from facility	Diversion increased: 6.2 min/pt boarded 4.6 min/pt admitted 9.9 min/hr of assess 11.3 min/hr of boarding	Admitted pt factor in amb diversion RN hours/MD on duty not a factor

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
The Association Between Length of Emergency Department Boarding and Mortality: A Multicenter Study. (Singer, et al, 2010)	Retrospective IDV: ED Boarding DV: Hosp LOS, mortality	Suburban Academic ED N=41,256	ED Boarding= Patients in ED >2 hours after admission Hosp LOS= days in hosp as inpatient Mortality= % of deaths	Hosp LOS: Increase from 5.6 days (<2 hours in ED) to 8.7 (>24 hours) Mortality: Increase from 2.5% (<2 hours in ED) to 4.5% (>12 hours in ED)	Incr hospital mortality and hospital LOS assoc w/ length of ED boarding.
Effect of Emergency Department Crowding on Outcomes of Admitted Patients. (Sun, et al, 2013)	Retrospective IDV: Hospital overcrowding DV: Inpatient mortality	187 non-federal California hospitals N=995,379	Hospital overcrowding: Defined by the proxy of ambulance diversion Inpatient mortality: percent odds of inpatient death	Inpatient mortality: 5% greater odds of inpatient death on days of high ED crowding	Periods of high ED crowding assoc w/incr inpatient mortality Assoc w/modest incr in LOS Assoc w/ incr costs for admitted patients.

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Effects of Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Patient Satisfaction and Reimbursement

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
Critical Quality Measures Finalized For Eligible Hospitals and Critical Access Hospitals Beginning With FY 2014. (CMS, 2014)	Guidelines	NA	NA	Added ED throughput measurements to reimbursement metrics	NA
The effect of emergency department crowding on patient satisfaction for admitted patients. (Pines, et al., 2008)	Retrospective cohort study IDV: ED boarding DV: Press-Ganey satisfaction scores	N=1501 hospitalizations	Press-Ganey Satisfaction Survey= validated, widely used satisfaction survey	ED hallway use=lower likelihood of recommendation, lower ED satisfaction, lower overall satisfaction (p<0.05) Prolonged ED boarding=lower ED satisfaction (p<0.05) Measures of ED crowding and ED waiting times predicted ED satisfaction (p<0.05)	A poor ED experience as measured by ED boarding time neg assoc w/ ED satisfaction predict lower satisfaction with the entire hosp Decrease ED boarding could improve pt satisfaction.
A Cross-sectional Study of Emergency Department Boarding Practices in the United States. (Pitts, et al, 2014)	Cross-sectional retrospective IDV: ED boarding times DV: Average ED visits	National Hospital Ambulatory Medical Care Survey N=139,502	ED boarding times= Time admitted patients spent in the ED after admission Average ED visits= Average number of annual ED visits per hospital in the quartile (in thousands)	National Median Boarding= 79min 1 st Quartile (0-24min)= 16.0 avg annual visits/hosp 2 nd Quartile (25-45min)= 18.4 avg annual visits/hosp	In nat'l survey, ED boarding of admitted pts disproportionately affects hospitals w/ higher ED volumes Prolonged ED boarding viewed as poor hosp perf Chosen as quality

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
				3 rd Quartile (46-86min)= 30.9 avg annual visits/hosp 4 th Quartile (87-410min)= 39.9 avg annual visits/hosp	measure in HVBP (affects reimbursement)
Patients Would Prefer Ward to Emergency Department Boarding While Awaiting an Inpatient Bed (Walsh, et al, 2008)	Cross-sectional survey Qualitative	County hospital ED N=1222	A survey tool was designed asking the subject, "If you needed to be admitted to the hospital but no inpatient bed is available, would you prefer to be kept in the ER hallway, or a hallway on an inpatient ward?"	Prefer inpatient hallway boarding= 801 (65.5%) Prefer ED hallway boarding= 406 (32.2%)	Boarded pts stated prefer to be boarded in the hallway of inpt ward rather than the ED

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Solutions for Overcrowding Table of Evidence-ED Beds

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
The Effect of Emergency Department Expansion of Emergency Department Overcrowding	Pre and post intervention study IDV: No. of ED beds DV: Ambulance diversion, ED LOS, admit hold LOS	Urban, academic tertiary care Level 1 ED	ED LOS= from triage to departure Admit hold LOS= admit decision to departure	ED LOS pre/post= 4.6/5.6 hrs Admit hold LOS pre/post= 3.0/4.1	Adding beds actually worsens times of interest
Adding more beds to the emergency department or reducing admitted patient boarding times: which has a more significant influence on emergency department congestion? (Khare, et al, 2009)	Computer simulation model IDV: Added ED beds, move patients DV: ED LOS	Modelled urban, academic, tertiary care, Level I trauma center N=5751	Constant ED rate of departure. Added ED beds: increasing number of beds from 23 to 28 Moving patients to floor: increasing admitted patient rate of departure from 1 pt/20 min to 1 pt/15 min ED LOS: time between sign-in and departure from ED	ED LOS; 23 beds, 1 pt/20 min= 240min 23 beds, 1 pt/15 min= 218min 28 beds, 1 pt/20 min=247min 28 beds, 1 pt/15 min= 225min	computer sim showed improving the rate at which admitted patients depart the ED= decreased ED LOS, increasing the number of ED beds did not.
Effects of emergency department expansion on emergency department patient flow. (Mumma, et al, 2014)	Retrospective study IDV: Increase in ED size from 33 to 53 beds DV: LWBS, ED boarding times	Academic medical center N=91254 Pre expansion N= 42896 Post expansion N=	LWBS= pt left ED before being seen by MD or physician extender ED boarding time= the interval from 1 hour	LWBS pre/post intervention= 9.0%/8.3% (p=0.053) ED boarding time= 160/180 (p=0.005)	More ED bed capacity associated w/no sig change in the percentage of patients who LWBT unintended

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
		48358	following admission bed request placement to the patient leaving the ED to the inpatient bed or operating suite. (hours/day)		consequence of an increase in ED boarding hours. ED expansion does not appear to be an adequate solution to ED crowding.

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Solutions for Overcrowding Table of Evidence-Inpatient DC

Article (Author(s), Year)	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results	Author's Conclusions, Study Limitations, Notes
The relationship between inpatient discharge timing and emergency department boarding. (Powell, et al., 2012)	Computer modeling IDV: Time of inpt DC DV: ED boarding times	Urban, tertiary care hospital N=4,776	Timing of inpt DC= Earlier DC 75% inp DBN All DC between 0800-1600	Shifting DC time 4 hr earlier eliminated ED boarding 75% DBN decreased ED boarding to 3.0 hrs	Ltd due to computer modelling Only top 3 timing factors